
Implementation of Value Clarification Technique (VCT) Learning to Improve Critical Thinking Characters

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ABSTRACT: This study seeks to evaluate the implementation of Value Clarification Technique (VCT) learning to improve the critical reasoning students' character of MI Islamiyah Syafiiyah Gandrirojo Kudus in Central Java. 5th class was chosen as the experimental group that applied VCT learning, and 6th class became the control group that applied conventional learning in Civics subjects, focusing on understanding citizens' rights, obligations, and responsibilities in everyday life. The research method used quasi-experiment. Data analysis shows a significant difference in the critical reasoning character of students who use VCT and conventional learning. This is evident through the results of a two-party t-test, where the t-count is smaller than the t-table ($-5.37 < -1.976$), meaning that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. In addition, the critical reasoning character of students who use VCT learning is also significantly higher than students who use conventional learning, as seen from the results of the one-party t-test with a t-count greater than the t-table ($8.47 > 1.664$). Thus, it can be concluded that VCT learning effectively develops the critical thinking character of students at MI Islamiyah Syafiiyah.

KEYWORDS: Learning Model, Value Clarification Technique, Critical Thinking Character

I. INTRODUCTION

Education is an urgent and crucial thing for humans. Humans can explore their personality, intelligence, skills, potential, noble character, talents, and expertise through education. (Khairuddin, 2022). Thus, education becomes the foundation of the process of human life (Deputy Vice-Chancellor for Postgraduate Studies and Research, Sultan Qaboos University, Oman, mrahma@squ.edu.om dkk., 2020; Hwang dkk., 2021).

The educational process is generally realized through learning, either within or outside the scope of formal learning. The learning process is dynamic, in which there are various characters of learners with diverse backgrounds and different levels of understanding among learners (Hwang dkk., 2021; Kamaruddin dkk., 2022).

Civic Education (PPKn) is a subject that aims to produce individuals who have a deep understanding of the rights and obligations of good Indonesian citizens. This subject's main goal is to create citizens who have a high level of intelligence, can innovate with creativity and have a character that is in line with the values of Pancasila and the principles contained in the 1945 Constitution (Asikin dkk., 2021). Therefore, Civic learning at the primary level can provide students with knowledge about life values. This aims to provide them with an understanding of values and moral education that can improve their social, national, and state life quality. The life values in question include students having sensitivity to phenomena that occur in society, having the courage to propose and explain their opinions logically in public, respecting diversity in the environment, thinking critically and logically, having creativity in dealing with life problems and civic issues, and using information and communication technology wisely, which is the ability to be innovative and intelligent in utilizing information and communication technology. For this reason, teaching Civics in SD/MI needs to be done with a significant intention and directed at instilling moral values in students. The main goal is that understanding these values is centered on the subject matter and can be applied and lived out in students' daily lives (Fell dkk., 2019; A. Maryam dkk., 2021; Siswinarti, 2019).

So far, in the context of basic education, learning activities still tend to be teacher-oriented. As a result, this kind of learning process limits learners' opportunities to develop independently through exploration and thinking processes. Teaching approaches that only flow in one direction often focus on memorizing concepts, but this is less useful for students when faced with real-world phenomena (Ermawati dkk., 2021).

Likewise, Civic learning only provides concepts and memorized material (cognitive aspects). Thus, educators must still emphasize the meaning and understanding of social values in the learning process (Fakhrudin dkk., 2013). As a result, there has been no formation of self-quality as an individual in students (Jerome & Kisby, 2022; Rahman dkk., 2022).

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We often encounter, so far, the approach commonly used by civics teachers, which is conventional methods such as lectures and question and answer. Teachers focus more on demanding students to memorize concepts but less on providing learning about how students should learn life values and solve problems (Dewantara, 2017). This type of learning results in a tendency for learners to be less active during the learning process. As a result, there needs to be more in developing learner competencies in the cognitive, affective, and psychomotor aspects. The impact is that most learners need help to relate the concepts taught in the classroom with practical ways of applying them in real-life situations. This causes learners to be less sensitive to their daily experiences and perceptions. Learners' passivity in learning will affect their low cognitive learning success. In addition, the lack of teacher expertise in choosing the right learning approaches and methods also impacts students' limited ability to reason critically and low cognitive learning outcomes in Civics learning (Dishon & Goodman, 2017; Nawawi dkk., 2020).

Similar learning processes are often found in MI Islamiyah Syafiiyah in Civics learning. This finding was revealed from the interviews, observations and recording documents of MI Islamiyah Syafiiyah students conducted on March 13-15, 2023. The interview results revealed several obstacles in implementing Civics learning, namely as follows: (1) Learners experience a tendency to be passive when participating in learning. (2) Learners need to be more comfortable to ask questions about problems they face during the teaching process. (3) Learners are reluctant to express their opinions. (4) Learners have yet to fully integrate the values they learn from Civic learning into their daily actions, so they are less sensitive to the phenomena that occur in their lives.

In addition to the interview and observation activities above, researchers also recorded documents. Document recording is taken from the average achievement of learning grades given by teachers in Civics subjects for classes V and VI MI Islamiyah Syafiiyah. The average value of Civics of MI Islamiyah Syafiiyah students in daily tests on understanding citizens' rights, obligations, and responsibilities in everyday life is 59.5. It is categorized in the low category if converted to Guideline Reference Assessment (PAP). As seen from the percentage of completeness, 58.24% of students still need to meet the expected standards in learning. This situation indicates that students' cognitive achievement in the Civics subject in MI Islamiyah Syafiiyah still needs improvement. The problem of low learning achievement requires serious attention.

Concerning the context of the problem mentioned earlier, one of the innovations applied to deal with this issue is to apply VCT learning in the Civics subject at MI Islamiyah Syafiiyah, especially in grades V and VI. Therefore, the researcher chose the research title "Implementation of the Value Clarification Technique (VCT) Learning Model in Improving Critical Reasoning Character and Student Learning Outcomes".

The results of previous studies that have been conducted by academics and researchers related to the implementation of the VCT learning model have been carried out by Novita Rukmala, Khairun Nisa, and Ilham, who found that the implementation of the model has a significant effect on the learning outcomes of Civics Class IV SDN 3 Peresak 2020 2020 (Dewi dkk., 2020). Similar research was also conducted by Pt. Ratih Siswinarti, who observed that the use of VCT learning using video media impacted the academic achievement of Civics of grade V elementary school students in Gugus III (Siswinarti, 2019).

Furthermore, research on the cultivation of critical thinking characters was conducted by Yuyun Dwi Haryanti and Budi Febriyanto. They found that applying the PBL learning model is relevant to practice in teaching at the SD / MI level to strengthen students' critical thinking skills (Haryanti & Febriyanto, 2017). Maryam, Kusmiyati, I Wayan Merta, and I Putu Artayasa also researched improving critical thinking using an inquiry learning model conducted in class XI MIA MAN 2 Mataram. They stated that using the inquiry learning model has significant benefits in developing students' critical reasoning attitudes (M. Maryam dkk., 2020).

Different from previous studies, this study focuses on the main objective, namely to evaluate the improvement of critical reasoning characteristics as a learning outcome of MI Islamiyah Syafiiyah students in Civics subjects through the implementation of the VCT learning model so that this research can add scientific variations and deepen stakeholders to develop learning, especially related to increasing students' critical reasoning.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Learning Pancasila and Citizenship Education (PPKn)

Civics is mainly an educational effort about ethics and morals. In the function of value education, Civics aims to support students in developing attitudes that include understanding, appreciation, and implementation of the values contained in the topic being discussed (Murniati Siti, 2019). The purpose of learning civics in SD / MI is to form students with good personalities as citizens. These individuals have an awareness of their rights and obligations and the ability to think critically about civic issues in their country. In addition, the goal also includes the motivation to keep up with the development of modern technology that is occurring terjadi (Azis, 2016).

Civics learning in SD/MI must be able to keep up with future developments (Azis, 2016). A paradigm shift in the learning process is an important factor in creating education that is relevant to future needs, namely from a focus on the teacher to a focus on students, adopting interactive and collaborative learning approaches, encouraging students to actively investigate the real world in a team or group framework, focusing on developing skills and empowering behaviors through the use of various multimedia

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sources and media, and shifting conventional learning towards cooperative learning. This goal also involves fostering critical, creative and innovative thinking skills, resulting in effective knowledge exchange (Bruggeman dkk., 2021; Dishon & Goodman, 2017; Hussein dkk., 2019).

Value Clarification Technique (VCT) Learning

Civics learning not only focuses on the cognitive aspects of individuals but also plays a role in shaping their affective aspects. Applying VCT learning is one of the strategies used in integrating affective learning in Civics. VCT is a method used to internalize and express specific values students own (Rachmadyanti & Rochani, 2017). Sanjaya added that VCT has an important role in helping learners explore and determine relevant values considered positive when facing situations or problems, carried out through analysis of existing values and internalized in themselves mereka (Wijayanti & Wasitohadi, 2015).

The VCT approach requires teachers to be able to guide learners to reveal the attitudinal values that already exist within them. In this process, learners are actively involved so that the values considered good can be implemented in their daily lives (DEWI, 2022; Spohrer & Bailey, 2020).

Critical Thinking Character

Critical thinking skills involve the ability to confront problems analyze information qualitatively and quantitatively before making decisions about the validity of the information (Kahfi, 2022). Through the practice of critical reasoning, learners can strengthen and develop their personalities to better withstand the influence of certain situations. They also learn to analyze information before accepting it or deciding (Kiska dkk., 2023). Critical reasoning has components that include obtaining and processing information and ideas, evaluating and assessing thinking, reflecting on thinking, and making decisions based on critical thinking and evaluation. These critical thinking skills will encourage students in Indonesia to have an inclusive mindset so that they will not be self-centered and can respect others. In decision-making, this ability will have a positive impact by producing benefits for oneself and others (Rahman dkk., 2022).

III. RESEARCH METHODS

The method applied in this study is the quasi-experimental method. The purpose of this method is to describe cause-and-effect interactions by including a control group and an experimental group (NurRahman, 2020). This study aims to compare students' learning achievement in two different learning models: VCT learning applied in the experimental class and conventional learning applied in the control class. The research design applied is Nonequivalent Control Group Design. Sugiyono argues that this design consists of two separate groups, namely the experimental and the control groups, where the two groups are not randomly selected (M.A, 2021). Figure 1 below shows the design used in this study.

Figure. 1

Sugiyono's Research Design (2015: 116)

Description:

X1 = VCT model learning process

X2 = Classical model learning process

O1 = pretest of the experimental class

O2 = posttest of the experimental class

O3 = pretest of the control class

O4 = posttest of the control class

----- = This line indicates that the groups were not chosen randomly but were based on predetermined classes.

In this study, the population included all students at MI Islamiyah Syafiiyah Gandrirojo. The sample consists of class V the e, an experimental class with 42 students, and class VI the c, the control class with 39 students. Population refers to the overall object of research with specific characteristics and is a data source for drawing conclusions kesimpulan (Cohen dkk., 2018; Ermawati dkk., 2021).

This study collected data using two techniques: tests and non-tests. Tests consisted of pretests and posttests, while non-tests included observations, interviews, and document collection. Tests were used to measure critical reasoning character using pretest and posttest assessments. The pretest was conducted before the learning materials were taught to students. This test aims to obtain

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information about the variation of the research sample penelitian (Mamondol, 2021). The posttest aims to identify whether there is an increase in learner achievement after undergoing the experiment.

The critical thinking skills test was carried out with an objective evaluation consisting of five description-type questions. This test was given before and after the learning process. The questions are given to all samples, namely classes V and VI, according to the concept that has been determined. The test sheet will be tested on experimental and control classes through pretest and posttest. After the test sheet is tested, the next step is to test the questions' validity, reliability, difficulty level, and differentiation. Descriptive questions are used to measure critical thinking skills based on predetermined indicators. The researcher then analyzed the critical reasoning ability categorized as high, medium, or low. Table 1 shows the scoring guidelines applied in the study.

Table 1. Critical Thinking Character Scoring Guidelines

No	Critical Thinking Indicators	Scoring	
		Problem	Score
1	Provide an easy-to-understand explanation (<i>elementary clarification</i>)	There is no simple explanation	1
		Incorrect explanation	2
		Almost perfect explanation	3
		Perfect explanation	4
2	Build <i>basic support</i> skills	No skills	1
		Improper skills	2
		Almost perfect skills	3
		Perfect skills	4
3	<i>Inference</i>	No conclusion	1
		Conclusions are not quite right	2
		Almost perfect conclusion	3
		Perfect conclusion	4
4	Provide further clarification (<i>advanced clarification</i>)	No further explanation	1
		Further explanation is not quite right	2
		Further explanation is almost perfect	3
		Further explanation is perfect	4
5	Design strategy and tactics	No strategy and tactics	1
		Improper strategies and tactics	2
		Strategy and tactics are almost perfect	3
		Perfect strategy and tactics	4

(Sakti, 2014)

Data from the test instruments, which included the pretest and posttest, were analyzed using descriptive statistical techniques. These statistics provide a detailed description of the data collected without generalizing about the data (Sugiyono, 2014). The descriptive analysis used descriptive statistics, such as preparing tables, graphs, and other calculations.

Number-shaped data is obtained through the process of assessing each student's critical thinking results. For subjective test data or descriptions are processed using the following formula:

Data in the form of numbers is obtained through the process of assessing the results of critical thinking from each student. For subjective test data or descriptions are processed using the following formula:

$$\text{Score} = \frac{\text{Scores obtained by students}}{\text{score maximum questions} \times \text{The Number of Questions}} \times 100$$

The average of the total scores obtained by students is calculated using the following formula:

$$\bar{X} = \frac{\Sigma fX}{n}$$

Information: \bar{X} = Ror average value obtained

ΣfX = Total overall student scores

n = Total number of learners

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IV. RESULTS

Implementation of the Value Clarification Technique (VCT) model

VCT refers to a learning model that focuses on the application of values to allow students to internalize these values and gain understanding and stability about these values (Muslich, 2022). This learning model seeks to help learners reflect on their feelings and actions to improve their awareness of their values.

VCT learning implemented in learning is carried out according to predetermined steps. According to Taniredja's explanation, the VCT model learning process consists of 7 stages that can be categorized into three levels. They are (Tibahary, t.t.):

The first level in this model is freedom of choice. In this level, there are three stages which can be explained as follows: (1) Learners are given the freedom to choose according to their judgment; (2) Learners are given choices from several available alternatives so that they can choose freely; (3) Learners are allowed to carry out analysis and consideration of the consequences that may arise as a result of their choice before making a selection.

The second level in this model is appreciation. This level consists of 2 stages of learning, which can be explained as follows: (1) Learners will have pride in the values they have chosen so that the values will become an integral part of their identity; (2) Learners will strengthen the values that have become an integral part of themselves by being brave and responsible to prove them publicly. In other words, if they feel the values are their choice, they will have the courage to show and prove the values in front of others.

The third level is doing. In this level, there are two stages: (1) Learners demonstrate the intention and capability to implement their choices; (2) Learners repeatedly repeat actions by their chosen values in their daily lives. The chosen values should be reflected and implemented in different expressions in every aspect of their lives.

Based on the observations, implementing VCT learning in Civics lessons in class V as an experimental class runs perfectly. This can be seen from the increase in assessment achievement at each meeting. These results show that researchers have optimally applied the VCT learning method.

Critical Thinking Character Learning Achievement

The critical thinking skills test in Civics lessons on understanding rights, obligations, and responsibilities as citizens in everyday life have been carried out by class V (experimental class), totaling 42 students, and class VI (control class), totaling 39 students. PVC learning was applied in the experimental class, and conventional learning was used in the control class. The critical reasoning character test was conducted pre-learning (pretest) and post-learning (posttest) in both classes.

Furthermore, pretest and post-test data were analyzed to obtain research conclusions regarding comparing students' critical reasoning skills in Civics lessons that apply VCT learning with conventional learning. This data is used to provide answers to research questions that have been formulated. The steps to analyze the values of critical reasoning skills are as follows: First, the pretest and posttest score data in the experimental class are presented; Second, the pretest and posttest score data in the control class are presented; Furthermore, test data analysis is carried out using the descriptive analysis method. This data is obtained by calculating the difference between pretest and posttest scores and then comparing it with the difference between the maximum score and pretest score of the two classes. The questions used in the pretest and posttest were similar, consisting of five questions that had to be answered in descriptions. Table 2 below contains the results of calculating the average, lowest, and highest scores on the pretest and posttest of the experimental and control group's critical thinking skills.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics of Pretest and Posttest Scores in Critically Reasoned Characters

Statistik	Experimental Class		Control Class	
	Pretest	Posttest	Pretest	Posttest
The Number of Students	42	42	39	39
Lowest Score	20	45	25	30
Top Score	75	95	75	80
Average	45,73	88,9	49,03	58,76

Source: Pretest will be held on March 27, 2023 and Posttest will be held on April 3, 2023

From the table presented above, it can be observed that the experimental class showed an average score of 45.73 out of 42 students at the pretest stage. Meanwhile, the control class had an average pretest score of 49.03 out of 39 learners, with the lowest score of 25 and the highest score of 75. In this case, the average pretest score achieved by the two classes did not differ much, indicating that the test results were initially relatively homogeneous between the two classes. On the posttest, the experimental class achieved an average score of 88.96 out of 42 learners. The lowest score was 45, and the highest score was 95. Meanwhile, the control class obtained an average posttest score of 58.76 out of 39 learners, with the lowest score of 30 and the highest score of 80.

Based on the description of the posttest results, there is a clear difference. The results of the critical reasoning ability test in the experimental class showed a higher score than the control class. This evidence is based on researchers' analysis of post-test data

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using an average difference test, a two-sided t-test and a one-sided test (right). The post-test data obtained showed a homogeneous distribution.

To make it easier to understand the data from Table 2, it can be concluded through Figure 2 that there is a significant difference between the pretest and posttest in the experimental class after the treatment. Meanwhile, the mean scores of the pretest and posttest in the control class did not show significant changes. The change can be seen based on the following diagram.

Figure 2. Diagram of the Average Score of Critical Thinking Character

Gambar 2. Diagram: Critical Reasoned Character Average Score

From the diagram presented, there is a slight or small difference between the pretest scores of the control class and the experimental classes' pretest scores. However, after being treated with innovative learning, namely VCT, there is a significant difference between the posttest scores of the experimental and control classes.

V. DISCUSSION

Analysis of pretest homogeneity data shows that the f-count value (0.043) is smaller than the f-table value (4.05); this means that the two sample groups are homogeneous. In this study, the learners' intelligence factor did not affect the results because from the pretest results, both classes showed homogeneity. This indicates that students from both classes have almost the same level of intelligence. In addition, the t-test results found that the t-count value (9.135) was greater than the t-table value (1.990). Therefore, there is a significant difference in posttest scores between the experimental and control groups at a certain level of significance.

Teaching in the experimental class with VCT learning begins with a series of activities, namely the teacher conveys greetings, prays, and takes students' attendance, and provides motivation and apperception as an introduction. Then, in the first stage of the activity, the teacher asked questions as a trigger to explore learners' knowledge about rights, obligations, and responsibilities as citizens in everyday life through question and answer discussions. Next, in the second stage, learners are classified according to their needs. The third stage involves a brief explanation from the teacher on the above material. In the fourth stage, the teacher provides each group stimulus in the form of stories or news related to the material. The fifth stage is clarification, where the teacher guides learners to think about the choices they would make in the story by considering the good and bad consequences. In the sixth stage, learners discuss in their groups to analyze the values contained in the narrative taught by the teacher, giving realistic considerations and strong reasons. The seventh stage involves presenting the discussion results from each group in front of the class. In the final stage, the teacher and learners collectively summarize the learning outcomes achieved, and the lesson is closed with a prayer together.

In the control class, learning is conventional. The material taught in the control class was similar to the material taught in the experimental class. In this model, the emphasis is more on the process of transferring knowledge to students without the active involvement of students in the value discovery process. In the control class, the teacher gives more explanations so that students have lower involvement and are more passive in the learning process.

The posttest results were given to both classes to evaluate the achievement in learning critical reasoning character in Civics subjects. In the experimental class, students achieved an average posttest score of 88.9. Meanwhile, the class in the control group achieved an average score of 58.76. The posttest data analysis process involved the application of a two-sided t-test showing that the t-count was smaller than the t-table ($-5.37 < -1.976$), so H_0 was rejected, which means there is a significant difference between the critical reasoning characters in the two learning models (VCT and conventional). In addition, the one-sided t-test showed that the t-count was greater than the t-table ($8.47 > 1.664$), so H_0 was rejected and H_a was accepted. This indicates that there is a significant difference in the average posttest scores. The experimental class's average posttest score significantly exceeded the control class's average posttest score. This finding shows that students who apply VCT learning have a higher level of critical reasoning tendency than students who apply conventional learning.

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VI. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings and discussion of research at MI Islamiyah Syafiiyah, the following conclusions are obtained:

There is a significant difference in the critical reasoning character of students who run VCT learning with students who run conventional learning. The results of the t-test calculation show that the data used in this study meet the assumptions of normal and homogeneous distribution, with a t-count value of 9.135 and a t-table of 1.990. Therefore, in a two-party test, the t-count value (-5.37) is smaller than the t-table value (-1.976), so H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted.

Students who follow VCT learning show higher critical reasoning characteristics than conventional learning. The t-test calculation results show that the data used in this study fulfill the assumptions of normality and homogeneity, with a t-count value of 9.135 and a t-table of 1.990. Therefore, in a one-sided test, the t-count value (8.47) is greater than the t-table value (1.664), so H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted.

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